

HEALTHY 01

Basic information on health and well-being

to enable you to learn more about health management

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Warsaw University
of Technology

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HEALTHY MODULE 1

Basic information on health and well-being

This unit aims to give you relevant knowledge, skills, and competences about basic concepts in health and well-being to enable you to learn more about health management.

What will you learn

- 1 You will understand what health and well-being mean.
- 2 You will learn how to differentiate between prevention and treatment.
- 3 You will learn crucial health management measures.
- 4 You will learn about health literacy.
- 5 You will learn how to support older people with their health and well-being.

Chapters summary

- 1 Introduction to health and well-being

- 2 Introduction to prevention and treatment

- 3 Health literacy

- 4 Healthy ageing

HEALTHY

MODULE 1

CHAPTER 1

Introduction to health and well-being

In the first chapter, you will learn the basics of health and well-being, practical tips for health management and different types of health care.

Introduction

Health and well-being are so important for us to have a happy life and reach our goals. It can be found in simple things as well.

For example, laughing can improve our mood and did you know that laughing 100 times is equal to 15 minutes on an exercise bike? Watching funny videos on YouTube has its benefits after all (but moderately!).

What will you learn

- 1 Well-being & health
- 2 Mental well-being
- 3 How to improve mental well-being

Meet Nikos

This is Nikos, a 50 year old who lives independently with his wife. He runs his own business, a shop, and he lives above the shop. However, Nikos struggles with some diseases, so throughout this unit we will count on you to help him.

Learn more about his health status & environment in the next slide!

Health status & environment

Positive

- Nikos lives independently with his wife.
- General medical support costs are covered by the National Health System.
- His council offers basic healthy lifestyle and exercise programs.
- Supportive friends help him in being more active.

Negative

- Nikos has diabetes and genetic cardiovascular diseases.
- He has non-routine work, which makes it difficult for him to follow his medication and lifestyle intervention (exercise, food) properly.
- He cannot pay for specialized/private healthcare.

“Health” and “well-being”

Grab a piece of paper and write down words that come to your mind when you think about health and well-being.

Take your time, there is no rush! When ready click on to the next slide.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 HEALTHY **MODULE 1** **CHAPTER 1**

How many of these did you write down?

- Success
- Happiness
- Joy
- Energy
- Benefit
- Wellness
- Gain
- Wholeness
- Fitness
- Prosperity

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 HEALTHY **MODULE 1** **CHAPTER 1**

Did we miss some words on the previous list?
Here's your chance to share some other words that you may have thought of!

What is health and well-being?

Here are the definitions according to the World Health Organization:

Well-being

“Well-being is the outcome from meeting an individuals’ essential needs and achieving goals and plans that an individual has in life.”

Health

“Not only the absence of illness but also a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being.”

Types of well-being

Let's learn more about well-being! Did you know there are several types of well-being? Here are 3 of the main types.

Emotional well-being

This refers to the ability of managing emotions, how we feel and see ourselves. It is related with being able to overcome obstacles in our life and loving ourselves.

Physical well-being

This is related with the functioning of your body, and how you feel about it. It is correlated with having a healthy lifestyle, including a balanced diet and moving your body.

Social well-being

This is our ability to have a support network, communicate with others and create meaningful relationships.

Mental well-being

It is extremely important to keep active, for your physical well-being. And you will find more tips in the training unit “Lifestyle and therapies”.

Now we want to talk about **mental well-being**. It is as important as physical well-being.

Mental well-being refers to your thoughts and feelings, and how you deal with life situations. In the next slides, you can find tips to enhance your mental well-being!

Meditation

Have you ever heard about it? It is a great and easy way to reduce stress, maintain mental well-being and increase concentration. One minute of meditation can make all the difference! Next, we will give you all the steps on how to meditate. Ready to find your inner peace?

Meditation

1**2****3**

Settle into your seat

You can sit on the floor or on a chair or if necessary, you can stay standing. The important thing is to feel where your body is touching the seat and/or touching the ground.

Meditation

1

2

3

Scan your body

Sit up straight or stand straight but not stiff. If sitting on a chair or standing, make sure your feet are completely touching the ground, connecting you to the earth. Your eyes are open, so take in the surroundings of where you are. Lower your gaze slightly.

Meditation

1

2

3

Connect with your breath

After acknowledging your surroundings, you can close your eyes and pay light attention to your breath as it goes out.

Meditation

Follow the out-breath

At the end of the out-breath, let there be a gap while the in-breath is happening. And in that gap, you have natural awareness: it's there already, you don't have to create it. So, follow the breath out, and out, and out. As thoughts arise, treat them as you would anything else you encounter: notice them, and use that noticing to bring you back to the out-breath and ride it out. Out, and out, and out. Repeat as many times as you wish.

Find out more

Resources

This exercise was retrieved from the mindful website – [healthy mind, healthy life](#). You can find more resources there on how to reduce stress and more mindfulness exercises.

Connect with other people

Whenever you can, be with friends, especially in-person. It is a great way to create positive memories and get emotional support! Here are some examples of what you can do:

- Call a friend you have not talked for a long time;
- Go to the cinema with someone;
- Go to the park with someone;
- Invite a friend to eat out with you.

Maybe what you want is to meet new friends, so you can do the activities above. Next, we give you tips on how to meet new people. Time to mingle!

Here are some tips!

Volunteer

Volunteering can help you meet people who share the same values as you. There are different types of volunteering opportunities for all ages and preferences. Do a quick search on what there is in your community and choose your favourite!

Join a club/group

There are different types of group/ clubs that you could join, such as book, dance, religious, walking, oh, the list is endless... Look for clubs in your community that you can join!

Take your dog to the park

If you have a dog, this is the tip for you! A shared love of pets is an instant conversation-starter. Go to a nearby park with your dog or a place where there is a lot of people walking by.

Facebook groups

On Facebook, there are local groups advertised that you can join. Just search for your town/city on the search bar and then click “groups”. There you will find activities happening in your community and individuals also eager to meet new people.

Learn new skills

Learning a new skill is a great way to raise self-esteem! It also increases your adaptability. However, it needs to be something you enjoy, and do not do it if it feels like an obligation. Here are some ideas:

- Play a new instrument;
- Learn a new language;
- Cook a new dish;
- Learn to knit;
- Learn new computer skills.

Did you know that people who learn a new skill are also less likely to develop dementia? We will learn more about dementia in a dedicated module. Please try our Smart learning units to see how technology can help.

Be physically active

Physical activity is not only great for physical well-being but can also enhance your mood. How awesome is that? There are some easy and simple physical activities you can do, let's check them out:

- Go for a 30-minute walk;
- Stretch your legs and arms;
- Instead of taking the lift, take the stairs;

You can also exercise while watching TV, 2 in 1! In the next slide let's learn some exercises you can do whilst watching your favorite tv shows!

Exercises you can do while watching your favourite TV show!

Here are some easy exercises you can do whilst watching TV. However, be careful when performing them and check with your doctor what is recommended for you.

Leg extensions

Sit up straight and at the edge of your seat. Hold on to the sides of your seat and lift your right leg so it is straight out in a knee-locked position. Bring it back down so your feet are planted on the ground. Do this 10 times, take a short break and repeat with your left leg.

Arm circles

Sit up straight with your feet planted on the floor. Extend your arms out on both sides. Circle your arms towards slowly. Do this as many times as you can, maximum 10 times before switching and circling in the other direction.

March

March in place or step side-to-side, or front-to-back.

Give to others

We've seen before that volunteering can be a great way to meet new people! Helping others creates positive feelings and a sense of reward! It boosts your self-worth as well. Some ways you can help:

- Donate at your local foodbank;
- Do a chore for someone;
- Send a nice message to someone;
- Spend some time chatting with older people at a care home.

Our pick – Vizinho Amigo

“Vizinho amigo” means friendly neighbor in Portuguese. When a COVID-19 lockdown was imposed in Portugal in March 2020, a group of friends (not from at risk groups) had the idea of volunteering to deliver groceries for their neighbors who were more vulnerable to COVID-19, so they did not need to leave their house. Volunteers put posters in their neighborhood and pamphlets in their neighbours’ mailboxes letting people know about the project and a contact number which they could call to avail of the service! How cool is that? You can join this movement by putting posters in your community, offering your help with daily tasks, such as walking the dog, delivering groceries etc.

Chapter summary

1

You have learned what health and well-being is.

2

You have learned how to improve mental well-being.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You have learned how to differentiate the different types of well-being.

2

You have learned how to improve well-being.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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HEALTHY | **MODULE 1** | **CHAPTER 2**

Introduction to prevention and treatment

In this chapter, you will learn about the basics of health management and treatment.

Introduction

According to WHO, people of all ages are vulnerable to the risk factors contributing to diseases. 71% of all deaths globally are the result of noncommunicable diseases, that could be prevented with an active lifestyle, such as a healthier diet, and paying attention to the health parameters. Let's dig into this in this chapter, so you can lead a healthy lifestyle!

What will you learn

- 1 Prevention vs treatment
- 2 Health management
- 3 Primary, secondary, tertiary care

Prevention vs Treatment

Recently, Nikos went for a health check and his doctor said his diabetes levels were very high and that Nikos needs to address this. But Nikos just knows about treatment, he does not know the difference between prevention and treatment. Can you help him?

Here you can find two definitions, try and guess which one means prevention, and which one describes treatment!

1. The action of stopping something from happening or arising.
2. Medical care given to a patient for an illness or injury.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 HEALTHY **MODULE 1** **CHAPTER 2**

Match prevention and treatment with the proper definition.

<p>Prevention</p>	<p>Action of stopping something from happening or arising. For example, eating less sugary foods.</p>
<p>Treatment</p>	<p>Medical care given to a patient for an illness or injury. For example, pills prescribed by the doctor to decrease Nikos' cholesterol levels.</p>

Prevention vs treatment

Here is the answer! Did you get it right?

Prevention: Taking action to prevent something from happening or arising. For example, eating less sugary foods , exercising, eating a balanced diet, to prevent chronic diseases that are caused by unhealthy lifestyles.

Treatment: Medical care given to a patient for an illness or injury. For example, pills prescribed by the doctor to decrease Nikos' cholesterol levels.

Health management

As you saw, prevention is key for an active and healthy life. There are simple things you can change in your lifestyle that diminish the risk of getting ill.

Following, we will learn some easy health management tips!

Keeping your hands clean is essential for keeping bacteria away and reduce the spread of diseases. In this video, you can learn how to handwash properly. Are you ready? After COVID-19, we are all trained and equipped to keep up with this habit, don't you think?

Activity 1 - Pepper experiment

Sometimes, it can be difficult to get others to wash their hands. Here is a fun experiment you can do to show others the importance of washing their hands! You just need a plate, water, pepper and washing liquid!

Healthy lifestyle

A healthy lifestyle, including healthy eating, is crucial to preventing diseases and continuing to have good health levels.

What do you think about the food in the photo? Should we eat it everyday?

Learn all about that and much more in our Lifestyle and therapy module!

Get screened

Getting screened is one of the best ways to prevent diseases from developing. Screenings help find health issues early on, when they may be easier to treat.

What are screenings?

Screenings are medical tests that medical staff use to check for diseases and health conditions before there are any signs or symptoms. Do not miss out on your health check ups and check with your doctor when your next one is due!

Screenings

Here are some easy things you can do without going to your GP to measure some health indicators. However, always discuss with your GP to know what is appropriate for you.

Blood pressure

It can be performed, at a pharmacy or at home with a blood pressure monitor. If you decide to do it at home, ask your GP what steps you need to follow so the measurement is accurate.

Weight

You can weigh yourself at home or go to the pharmacy to have it done. It is better to weigh yourself with minimal clothing when you wake up. What about picking a day and start doing that on a weekly basis?

Diabetes

Diabetes levels can be measured at home with a blood glucose monitor. Talk with your doctor to see if this would be useful for you to record your blood glucose!

Sleeping

If you do not sleep well and for the number of hours recommended, it can have a serious impact on your health. It increases the likelihood of some diseases such as diabetes and decreases life expectancy. Moreover, it affects your mood and mental well-being. It is recommended you sleep 8 hours a day.

Remember Nikos? He has been having trouble sleeping 8 hours a day and has trouble falling asleep. What about you?

Let's help Nikos with his night time routine!

Sleeping

Here are some actions Nikos' can take. Which ones do you think are appropriate to help him sleep better? Let's play a quiz!

- Consume caffeine late in the day
- Try to sleep and wake at consistent times
- Get a comfortable bed, mattress, and pillow
- Be on the phone one hour before bed
- Keep the lights down if you get up during the night
- Listen to soft music before going to bed

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 HEALTHY | **MODULE 1** | **CHAPTER 2**

Consume caffeine late in the day

True

False

Answers

1

Do not consume any caffeine at night

Caffeine consumed late in the day, can affect your nervous system and may stop your body from naturally relaxing.

Nikos loves drinking coffee after dinner; however, he will start drinking decaffeinated coffee from now on.

2

3

Answers

1

2

3

Try to sleep and wake up at consistent times

Waking up and going to bed at similar times, helps create a routine in the long-term and after a while, you might not even need an alarm!

Nikos will start going to bed at 11pm and waking up at 7am.

Answers

1

2

3

Get a comfortable bed, mattress, and pillow

Did you know you should upgrade your bedding at least every 5–8 years? Also, having the right temperature in the room is essential, not too cold, not too warm.

Nikos bought a more comfortable pillow to help him sleep better!

Answers

—
↓
4

↓
5

↓
6

Do not be on your phone two hours before bed

To improve sleeping you should not be in front of screens and you should turn off all bright lights two hours before going to bed.

Nikos used to read and answer emails from customers until late in the night. From now on, after dinner he will not be on his laptop, (nor his cellphone!)

Answers

—

4

5

6

Keep the lights down if you get up during the night

You should minimize the number of times you need to get up during the nights, for example do not drink too much liquid, such as water, in the hours before going to bed. If you get up, keep lights down.

Nikos decided to drink the recommended amount of water during the day and less water at night so he does not wake up so often to go to the toilet.

Answers

Listen to soft music before going to bed

As we learned we should not watch tv or use any type of screens before going to bed. However, it is a great time to listen to some relaxing music, take a shower or take time for a quick mindfulness moment!

Nikos is organising a playlist to listen to when relaxing at night, do you have any suggestions for him?

Primary, secondary, tertiary care

About care and treatment, did you know there are different types of care? Let's learn the difference!

Primary care

This refers to the essentials. This is the first point of contact for your symptoms and medical concerns. (Your GP)

Secondary care

When your primary care provider refers you to a specialist, someone that has more expertise in what health care you need.

Tertiary care

This is when health care needs highly specialized equipment and expertise, for example when you are hospitalized.

Chapter summary

1

You have learned the difference between prevention and treatment.

2

You have learned how to prevent diseases.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You have learned how to identify health risk situations and how to prevent them

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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HEALTHY | MODULE 1 | CHAPTER 3

Health literacy

In this chapter, you will learn all about health literacy and how to improve it.

Introduction

In the European Health Literacy Survey, 12% of the respondents have inadequate health literacy and 35% are in the problematic health literacy range. Adequate health literacy is crucial for improving health levels and reducing inequities in that realm. For instance, according to WHO, health literacy is a major factor in preventing noncommunicable diseases, also known as, chronic diseases, which we will learn more about in another module with the same name.

What will you learn

- 1 Health literacy
- 2 Benefits of health literacy
- 3 Improving health literacy in your community
- 4 “Message in a bottle” project
- 5 How to create your own “Message in a bottle” project

What is health literacy?

It is extremely important that people understand and analyze basic health information needed to make appropriate health decisions. This is called **health literacy**. It is also about people having the knowledge about what they need to change in their lifestyles and living conditions to improve personal and community health.

Which situations do individuals with low health literacy have difficulties with?

Looking for specialized support

When individuals need help for a health condition, they might not know where they can find the support they need.

Filling health forms

Sometimes health forms are complex and use terms individuals do not know.

Understanding medication intake

One of main challenges for patients with low health literacy is understanding how and when to take their medication.

Managing chronic diseases

Managing a chronic disease can be hard if you do not have the information you need, including knowing the connection between risk behaviours and health and what information to share with the medical team.

Which ones are true which ones are false?

After learning about what health literacy is, let's play a true or false game. You can find some statements below, which ones are true? Which ones are false? Let's play a quiz!

- ✓ High rates of health literacy in population groups benefit societies.
- ✓ Limited health literacy significantly affects health.
- ✓ Low health literacy can reinforce existing inequalities.
- ✓ Building personal health literacy skills and abilities is not a lifelong process.
- ✓ Capacity and competence related to health literacy vary according to context, culture and setting.
- ✓ Health literacy improves responsiveness of health systems.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 HEALTHY | **MODULE 1** | **CHAPTER 3**

High rates of health literacy in population groups benefit societies

True

False

How to improve your health literacy

Ask, ask, ask

Ensure you ask the medical staff all the doubts you have. It is important you are informed and understand how to take care of yourself.

Repeat information back

After a medical professional gives you guidance or information, repeat the information back to him/her in your own words. It is a great way to ensure you understand everything correctly.

Visual support

Images, graphs, videos and other visual formats, can help with understanding information better. Ask your medical staff for hand-outs or other materials you can take home to study, or also search the internet (don't forget to check if it is a reliable source!).

Ask for an interpreter

If you do not speak the language of the country where you are receiving health care, ask for an interpreter in your preferred language to make sure you understand everything.

Activity 2

Nikos thinks that in his community health literacy is very low amongst people and he would like to improve it. As we have seen before, visual aids can be a great way to help people better understand health information. He thought about creating health management posters to put up in his shop. Can you help him?

Activity 2

First, choose one topic that you learned about in this unit. From that topic, what would you like to write on the poster? Ensure you use simple language and short phrases.

Secondly, the graphic part! You can use simple and free tools such as paint or [canva](#). In canva you can find cool layouts in which you just have to add the information or more clipart.

You can add some images, there are websites with free images, such as [freepik](#), [Centre for Ageing Better](#) and [Unsplash](#).

OR! Grab a cardboard and some crayons!

#FicaEmCasa

Quando usar máscara?

Fonte: Organização Mundial da Saúde

Tossiu ou espirrou?

NÃO SIM

Está a cuidar de uma pessoa suspeita de estar infetada com Covid-19?

NÃO SIM

Use máscara para sua segurança e para segurança dos demais.

Não necessita de usar máscara, mas não se esqueça de lavar frequentemente as mãos. Se tem máscaras de que não necessita, pode dá-las àqueles que mais delas necessitam, como é o caso dos profissionais de saúde.

As máscaras apenas são eficazes se, paralelamente as mãos com um desinfetante à base de álcool ou as lavar com água e sabão.

Illustration of a hand holding a red surgical mask, a hand holding a bottle of hand sanitizer, and a healthcare worker and a patient wearing masks.

Good practice - Message in a bottle

This is a project created by Lions International in which people keep all the essential personal and medical information, inside a bottle.

Then, the bottle is stored inside the fridge and there is a sticker at the individual's home door alerting emergency services personnel that that person has a bottle in the fridge with all the important information. This allows for quicker and better understanding of the individual's health for emergency staff. This is great idea for people with chronic and life-threatening diseases.

Activity 3

Message in a bottle is such a great idea, right? Why not implement it in your community? Or maybe start your own business? Let's get to action and think about how you can do it.

Activity 3

1

2

3

Where can you get bottles?

Think about where you can get bottles. Maybe you can create a partnership with a business that will sponsor bottles? Or you can recycle old bottles with some friends? Think about other options/resources you might have in the community.

Activity 3

1

2

3

Create a form

Now, you need to create a form for people to fill in and put it inside the bottle. Which information do you think is relevant to include? Maybe you can ask health professionals for help. And where can you print the forms?

Activity 3

1

2

3

Get the stickers

This is a very important step, so emergency staff know about the bottle. Who can create the stickers? Where can you print them? Maybe you can create a partnership with a business?

Activity 3

4

5

6

Get spaces where people can get the bottles and forms

Think about where people can collect the material (bottles and forms) to participate in the project in your community. Grocery shops? Health centres? Supermarkets? Pharmacies?

Activity 3

—

4

5

6

Inform emergency services

Contact emergency services in your area to let them know if they see the project's sticker at people's houses, it means they have a bottle in their fridge with basic health and personal information!

Activity 3

Inform people

When you have all the previous details finalised, it is time to inform people about the project and how they can join. What do you think will be the best way to do this? Some ideas are to put up posters in community places and/or information sessions.

Chapter summary

1

You have learned the basic of health literacy

2

You have learned what can be done to improve health literacy

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You have learned how to identify low health literacy situations

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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HEALTHY

MODULE 1

CHAPTER 4

Healthy Ageing

In this chapter, you will learn about older people, some needs that might arise due to age and how to help them if needed!

Introduction

Life expectancy is increasing globally, which means people are living for more years than before and some different needs might arise. Although, there is no such thing as an a typical older person, it is important to foster active ageing to ensure quality of life at all ages.

Let's learn more about healthy ageing and the role of the community in this process!

What will you learn

- 1 Misconceptions about older people
- 2 Loneliness in older people
- 3 How to support older people

Some facts

According to the World Health Organization, between 2015 and 2050, the proportion of the world's population over 60 years will nearly double from 12% to 22%.

By 2020, the number of people aged 60 years and older will outnumber children younger than 5 years. Are you surprised?

Ageism

Have you ever heard about Ageism?

It refers to the stereotypes, prejudice and discrimination towards someone or a group based on age. Ageism affects all ages, although most commonly affects older people.

There are many stereotypes we might have about older people that are wrong, let's play a quiz!

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 HEALTHY | **MODULE 1** | **CHAPTER 4**

There is no typical older person

True

False

Loneliness in older people

Older people are especially vulnerable to loneliness and social isolation – and it can have a negative effect on their health.

Here are some reasons for loneliness:

- Getting older or weaker
- Retirement
- The deaths of spouses and friends
- Disability or illness

Activity 5

Nikos found out that Maria's knit club has closed, and it was her favourite activity of the week.

Nikos has noticed that his 84-year-old neighbor Maria has been a bit sad lately. She used to pass through his shop every day to wish him good morning. But not recently.

Thus, she feels lonely and cannot socialize with others.

What do you think Nikos can do to help Maria? Write down your answer.

Here are some tips!

Start a conversation

You've learned that social and mental well-being is very important. Talking to someone is important, take this next step and chat with your neighbour!

Offer practical help

Older people might have mobility issues, ask them if they need help with tasks, for example shopping and getting medication.

Share a meal

Some older people may need help cooking. Why not cook a delicious meal for them and go over to their house? Or share fruits and vegetables in season with them? Lay a hand and avoid food waste!

Watch out for signs of winter illness

Make sure they take the flu jab and their house is prepared for the cold.

Did you know?

October 1st is International Day of Older Persons! The day was created to raise awareness about issues affecting older people and their amazing contributions to society.

Falls

According to WHO, falls are the second leading cause of unintentional injury deaths worldwide. Moreover, a fall can cause severe chronic disability. An estimated 684 000 individuals die from falls globally, age being a common risk factor.

Did you know most falls can be prevented? Yes, it is true! Some of the causes for older people falling are decreased hearing and eyesight; less strength and balance, unsuitable footwear. Moreover, there are risk factors in the physical environment, such as bad lighting. You will learn more about fall preventions at home in another module. Now, we will see some small changes you can do, especially in your health habits to reduce the likelihood of falling. This advice is useful for all of us, as healthy ageing is a process and not a state!

Tips

Medication control

Medication, on its own, or combined, can sometimes cause side effects, such as dizziness, that increase the risk of falling. If you are having side effects, speak with your doctor. Moreover, always follow the intake guidelines, such as time and dosage.

Hearing

If you notice changes in hearing, contact your doctor. It could be just an accumulation of wax or you might need a hearing aid. Nonetheless, you should get your ears checked every year.

Eyesight

Always wear your prescription glasses, if you do not wear glasses, and notice changes in your eyesight, talk with your doctor. Moreover, you should get your eyes checked every two years!

Healthy lifestyle

We've spoken about this countless times in this module! Having a healthy diet and exercising is extremely important to maintain muscle strength. Furthermore, high levels of Vitamin D (which you can get from sunlight and foods such as egg yolks and salmon) reduce the risk of falling. Learn more in Lifestyle and Therapy!

And much more...

You can learn more on how to help those who live with dementia, cognitive or physical impairments, or a chronic disease in the upcoming modules. Keep in mind, there is no typical older person, each individual is unique, and so is each older person!

Hands full and hands -on: list of useful contacts and links

Here you can find some useful contacts in your country

✓ European emergency phone number, available everywhere in the EU, free of charge: 112

✓ National health number, free of charge, 24h: 808 24 24 24

✓ National social emergency helpline, free of charge, 24h: 144

✓ SOS friendly voice, from 16h-24h:

213 544 545 - 912 802 669 - 963 524 660

✓ Citizen's public online services portal:

<https://eportugal.gov.pt/cidadaos#section-238338>

✓ National Health Service Website:

<https://www.sns24.gov.pt/>

Chapter summary

1

You have broken stereotypes you might have had about older people

2

You have learned about ageism

3

You have learned what health actions can be taken to prevent falls

4

You have learned some specific needs of older people

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You have learned how to identify a few of the needs from some older people

2

You have learned how to tackle loneliness

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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Module summary

1 Health and well-being and the importance of health literacy

2 The difference between prevention and treatment

3 Crucial health management measures

4 Care and support for the older people with their health and well-being

Module completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this module!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You got to know more about the importance of physical and mental well-being

2

You learned about health literacy and how to look after yourself and others

3

You've learned about Healthy Ageing: how to combat ageism and create an age-friendly community

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this module or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)